

RESEARCH ARTICLE OPEN ACCESS

Evaluating CORDEX-CORE Climate Projections for Simulated Hydrological Processes in a Mesoscale Catchment, South Africa

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Received: 19 September 2025 | **Revised:** 28 January 2026 | **Accepted:** 1 February 2026

Keywords: climate projections | CORDEX-CORE | hydrological flow components | J2000 | Mediterranean climate

ABSTRACT

Understanding future streamflow and changes to hydrological processes is one of the common uses of hydrological models. But the uncertainty of different warming scenarios, boundary conditions and extent of Earth System Models (ESMs) impacts how future conditions might translate into changes in hydrological processes and streamflow. We hypothesise that the coarse spatial resolution of readily available CORDEX-CORE simulations (25 km) will either under- or overestimate streamflow in small, mesoscale, heterogeneous catchments (< 700 km²), relative to hydrological models driven by local station data, due to the inability of projections to capture steep headwater-valley climate gradients. Additionally, we test whether the selection of ESMs exerts a stronger influence on the sensitivity of hydrological model parameters than the choice of downscaling method. We focus on the near future (2024–2053) because projections for the far future (e.g., 2100) carry even greater uncertainty. To evaluate these hypotheses, we applied the J2000 rainfall-runoff model to the Eerste River catchment using the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) 2.6 and 8.5 scenarios for the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5) for 2006–2053. The simulations were driven by both CORDEX-CORE ESMs as well as local climate station data to allow for performance benchmarking. The results of the application highlight the reduced skill of J2000 when driven by projected input data compared to using local station data, particularly in simulating high flows. The most likely cause of this is the inability of the coarse resolution of CORDEX-CORE (25 km) to capture the vast differences in climate between the headwater and valley within the Eerste, which is spatially variable. Using the CORDEX-CORE projections as input into the hydrological model, there were, however, decent representations of simulated low flows. The sensitivity analysis showed that J2000 model parameters were more influenced by the selection of the ESMs than downscaling using the Regional Spectral Models, highlighted by more sensitivity to scaling of the air capacity of the soil module. Exploratory analyses of future hydrological conditions suggest a mean annual flow reduction of 10%–22% (Q1–Q3) under RCP 2.6 compared to 8%–26% (Q1–Q3) under RCP 8.5 for the near future (2024–2053). While most (66%) projections suggest that the high flows will likewise be reduced, there is a low percentage (33%) of projections that suggest an increase in high flows under RCP 8.5 for the near future. Many of the projections suggest a further extension of the dry season (66%) and the wet season could be moved by 1–2 months later, compared to the historical conditions where June typically represents the mid-winter period. The simulated hydrological flows suggest a reduction in baseflow and interflow, but high-resolution projections (≈5–10 km) are required to improve the agreement in the historical projections compared to observed data.

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1 | Introduction

Mediterranean climatic regions are climatologically unique and exhibit strong contrasts between dry summers and mild, wet winter seasons (Eshel 2002). In these regions, precipitation often falls in a short 3-month period, driving hydrological process variability between the dry and wet seasons, seasonal water deficits and presenting a constant challenge for water management (Burak and Margat 2016). The provision of water for domestic, industrial and agricultural sectors and the allocation to the environment (ecological reserve) depend on the variability of this short-wet period, as well as the ability to store water in reservoirs and aquifers for the dry season (Hughes 2006). The vulnerability of Mediterranean regions due to strong contrasting seasons makes it important to understand the impact of future climate projections on hydrological processes so that climate change risks can be identified. The necessity of environmental and agricultural releases from reservoirs plays a crucial role in maintaining river ecosystem function and supporting crop production. However, recurring failures of centralised water supplies in many Mediterranean climatic regions (e.g., Jack et al. 2022; Watson, Miller, et al. 2022) require the development of robust simulations of future hydrological flows and impacts on hydrological processes.

Recent developments and improvements in Earth System Models (ESMs), successors to Global Climate Models (GCMs), aim to incorporate more relevant aspects of the Earth system by considering physical, chemical and biological processes, in addition to physical atmospheric and oceanic factors (Flato 2011). These developments have been made through the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) for the world and Africa. For South Africa, efforts have mainly been focused on country-wide future streamflow projections, utilising CCAM ensembles under RCP 4.5 and 8.5 to drive rainfall-runoff modelling (Schulze et al. 2005; Schütte et al. 2023). However, with the exception of lumped monthly water balances (Du Plessis and Kalima 2021; Kibii and Du Plessis 2024), the different climate projections from CORDEX have not been used to assess the change in future streamflow and hydrological processes for Mediterranean Southern Africa (Western Cape), as well as the associated impacts on water supply.

There is considerable variability between the different ESMs across the world, their respective downscaled Regional Spectral Models (RSMs) and different Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) (van Vuuren et al. 2011). In the Mediterranean climate of the Western Cape, South Africa, these uncertainties are lower as the mechanisms behind the widening of the Hadley cell, due to anticipated warming, are more certain than in other climate types (Burls et al. 2019). While the availability of only the 2.6 (conservative) and 8.5 (extreme) RCPs for the African domain limits the ability to assess an intermediate scenario, the deviation of RCP 8.5 only differs after 2050 from the intermediate RCP 4.5 scenario; therefore, the CORDEX projections provide a means to constrain the most likely near-future impact (to 2050). Despite accounting for important regional features, regional climate projections are still subject to systematic errors and therefore require bias correction to better capture regional observed climate conditions (Gudmundsson et al. 2012).

The Mediterranean Western Cape of South Africa receives most of its rainfall in the form of frontal events with occasional cut-off lows driving extremes and high surface runoff (de Waal et al. 2017). The winter months June, July and August together account for 50% of the total annual runoff (Watson, Midgley, et al. 2022). Due to strong orographic lifting, the high mountainous regions of this Mediterranean climate zone receive a disproportionate amount of rainfall, up to three times more compared to catchment valleys in other parts of the Mediterranean Western Cape (Watson, Birkel, et al. 2024). Additionally, mountainous regions support the bulk of the baseflow generation during the dry season. As such, mountain headwaters are critical zones for hydrological inputs and processes in the region. Microclimates drive differences in hydrological processes between mountains and valleys in this region, including differences in evapotranspiration, interflow and baseflow, which are impacted by differences in aspect, slope, lapse rates, thickness of the unsaturated zone and the presence of fractured rock aquifers (Watson, Birkel, et al. 2024). We hypothesise that the coarse resolution of CORDEX-CORE projections may not fully resolve microclimatic differences, potentially under- or overestimating the importance of mountainous headwaters. As a result, determining whether climate projections and their corresponding resolutions can distinguish between valley and mountainous variations is essential for regions with high topographic gradients, but also regions that are vulnerable due to a short-wet season.

In this study, we drive the JAMS/J2000 fully distributed rainfall-runoff model for the Eerste River catchment (Watson, Midgley, et al. 2021) with climate projections from CORDEX-CORE. The Eerste River is one of the smallest quaternary catchments in the Mediterranean Western Cape, which has a significant proportion of its area dominated by mountainous hydrological processes. We test the impact of driving bias-corrected climate projections on simulated streamflow results, hydrological flow components (baseflow, interflow and surface runoff) and parameter uncertainty, compared to simulations using locally collected weather data. As increases in drought occurrence and intensity are expected in Mediterranean catchments such as the Eerste River, developing a consensus of the anticipated impacts on hydrological processes is needed for adaptation. As these projections are coarse in terms of resolution (25 km) impacting the inclusion of local atmospheric processes, we compare the impact monthly (as the standard model runs on a daily timestep) with the following specific objectives and workflow (Figure 1):

- (1) Bias-correct the climate change projections using quantile mapping (Gudmundsson et al. 2012) and evaluate the effectiveness of different quantile mapping techniques;
- (2) test whether the bias-corrected CORDEX-CORE projections systematically under- or overestimate simulated hydrological flows compared to simulations driven by local station data.;
- (3) assess the impact of the CORDEX-CORE projections on simulated streamflow and hydrological flows under RCP 2.6 and 8.5 for 2024–2053;
- (4) compare the uncertainty of using the projections as inputs versus locally collected weather data for the JAMS/J2000 model and
- (5) provide a consensus across all the models on the likely future scenarios for 2024–2053.

2 | Environmental Setting

The Jonkershoek sub-basin (Figure 2) is situated in the Mediterranean climate of South Africa, with warm, dry summers and wet winters (winter rainfall zone) (Van Rompaey et al. 2001; Watson, Midgley, et al. 2021). The Jonkershoek is located at the headwaters of the Eerste River catchment, which drains east into the Atlantic Ocean with an estuary present at the catchment's outlet (Watson, Midgley, et al. 2021). The

catchment is 620 km² in size and includes the Kleinplaas Dam (0.37 Mm³) in the Jonkershoek headwaters, the Stellenbosch Wastewater Treatment Works (capacity 35 ML/day) and Faure (capacity 500 ML/day) treatment works, located in the middle and outlet of the catchment, respectively.

The plateau above the valley receives the highest rainfall averages in South Africa, > 3500 mm per year, with the mouth of the valley receiving averages of around 1000 mm per year

FIGURE 1 | Workflow diagram showing the processes of data collection from ESGF (Earth System Grid Federation), bias correction using quantile mapping of projections (PTF: parametric transformation, QUANT: empirical quantile, RQUANT: robust empirical quantile, SSPLIN: smoothing splines), data used in the development of a base hydrological model with calibration and validation criteria (Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency in standard form: NSE; Nash and Sutcliffe 1970, logarithmic form: logNSE, the Kling Gupta Efficiency: KGE, Gupta et al. 2009 and Bias) and the analysis of near future hydrological projections and parameter uncertainty.

FIGURE 2 | Location of the Western Cape within (a) Africa and (b) South Africa, (c) the Eerste River catchment, (d) mean annual precipitation (MAP: Lynch, 2003), including the town of Stellenbosch, water treatment works (Faure) and Stellenbosch water treatment plant (SWTP), streamflow gauging stations, available climate and precipitation stations (after Watson, Birkel, et al. 2024; Watson, Kralisch, et al. 2024), Kleinplaas Dam and the resolution of the CORDEX-CORE Earth System Models under Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5.

TABLE 1 | Description of GCMs used in this study, their location of origin and their corresponding resolutions (Borzorg-Haddad 2022).

Model	Institute and country of origin	Resolution Earth System Model	
		Atmosphere (LAT×LON)	Ocean (LAT×LON)
HadGEM 2-ES	Met Office Hadley Center, United Kingdom	1.0×1.0	1.9×1.2
MPI-ESM-LR	Max Planck Institute (MPI), Germany	1.5×1.5	1.9×1.9
MPI-ESM-MR	MPI, Germany	0.4×0.4	1.9×1.9
NorESM1-M	Norwegian Climate Centre (NCC), Norway	1.1×0.6	2.5×1.9

(Lynch 2003). Approximately 80% of the rainfall in the catchment occurs in the 7-month wet season (April–October), brought about by long-duration, low-intensity, frontal storm systems (Slingsby et al. 2021). This climate is a consequence of the location of the southern African continent in relation to the band of westerly waves and the subsequent associated low-pressure systems that travel west to east at roughly 40° and 50°S (Midgley et al. 2003). The low-pressure systems bring rainfall to southwestern South Africa seasonally, due to the position of the westerly waves, in the form of cold fronts. Frontal rainfalls are often enhanced by the orographic effects of the Cape Fold mountains in the region (Midgley et al. 2003). As a result, precipitation over the southwestern region may be classified as the orographic and stratiform type that is associated with mid-latitude frontal structures. Most of the rainfall received in the broader Eerste catchment occurs in the Jonkershoek, with the rest of the catchment being relatively dry, which illustrates the impact of orographic precipitation in the region (Figure 2d). The catchment falls within the Cape Fold belt, a sequence of sedimentary rocks deposited in the Paleozoic Era (Compton 2004). The mountains are dominated by the Table Mountain Group Sandstones, while the valley is characterised by the Tygerberg formation, comprised mainly of shales, fine-grade greywacke and quartzite. In low-lying areas of the catchment, the Cape Granite Suite has intruded into the Tygerberg formation. Average groundwater recharge estimates range from 13% to 27% of mean annual precipitation (MAP) for the TMG and 6%–8% of MAP for the valley. The predominant land use in the catchment is cultivated vines, as much of the catchment has been converted into agriculture, although Jonkershoek is dominated by alien plantation (mainly Pine species). Fire events in the Jonkershoek have impacted catchment hydrology, impeding infiltration and percolation, which causes greater overland flow to be generated as well as reduced hydraulic conductivity (Midgley and Scott 1991).

3 | Data and Methods

3.1 | Extraction of Climate Projections

The Hadley Centre Global Environmental Model version 2 (HadGEM2-ES), Max Planck Institute Earth System Model (MPI-ESM) and the Norwegian Climate Centre's Earth System Model version 1 (NorESM1-M) (Jalota et al. 2018) were the ESMs available for Africa at a daily timestep at 0.22×0.22 horizontal resolution (~25km) from CORDEX-CORE (Table 1). The available CORDEX-CORE RSMs include the Regional Model version 15 REMO 2015, developed by the Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS); the fourth generation Regional Climate Model

RegCM4-v7, developed by the Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics (ICTP) and the COSMO Climate Limited-area Modelling Community CCLM5.

Meteorological variables were obtained through the Earth System Grid Federation CORDEX database. The variables included near-surface mean, minimum and maximum temperature as well as near-surface wind speed (m/s), solar radiation (RN) (W/m²), near-surface relative humidity (RH) (%) and daily precipitation (mm). These variables were obtained for three evaluation runs, namely, RCP 2.6, RCP 8.5 and the historical run driven by ERA-Interim, with the appropriate units of each grid cell (0.22×0.22) being converted into station points (using the centroid of each cell). As a result, five stations for REMO and CCLM 5 and six stations for RegCM4 v-7 were extracted (Figure 2d). Observed data from gauges were supplied by numerous weather stations from sources such as the South African Weather Service (SAWS), Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON), as well as private climate station data from iLeaf (Hortex). The observed data were available within the existing JAMS/J2000 Eerste River model (Watson, Kralisch, et al. 2024) and have been regionalized within the JAMS to the area of the grids of the netCDF down-scaled projections.

3.2 | JAMS/J2000 Rainfall–Runoff Model

Amongst the multitude of models available in the literature, the JAMS/J2000 model (Krause 2002; Krause and Kralisch 2005) can be distinguished as an open-source process-oriented hydrological model that depicts climate data regionalization, volumetric soil water balance and propagations into water flows (de Cardoso Salis et al. 2019). The JAMS/J2000 is designed for river basin modelling of rainfall-runoff processes that set provisions for the evaluation of natural and anthropogenic factors involved in water balance and flood generation (Jeleapov et al. 2014). The modelling component with the highest temporal dynamics is the fast direct surface runoff (RD1) overland flow, which refers to runoff over sealed areas and surface runoff caused by saturated access and infiltration overflow runoff (Watson, Midgley, et al. 2022; Watson, Miller, et al. 2022). The slow direct runoff component (RD2), commonly known as interflow, corresponds to lateral hypodermic runoff within the soil zone, which reacts slightly slower than fast direct runoff (Machado et al. 2016). Furthermore, two baseflow components can be distinguished. The first is 'fast' baseflow runoff (RG1), which simulates flow from the upper

FIGURE 3 | A model schematic of the JAMS/J2000 showing an overview of the main components and the climate model inputs (temperature [T: min, max, mean], windspeed [U], relative humidity [RH], solar radiation [RN] and precipitation) as well as reservoir component (after Watson, Birkel, et al. 2024; Watson, Kralisch, et al. 2024).

part of the aquifer (the weathered layer of the hydrogeological unit), which is more permeable due to weathering (Machado et al. 2016). Finally, the ‘slow’ base flow runoff component (RG2) refers to slow groundwater flow within fractured solid rock or matrix in homogeneous unconsolidated aquifers such as shale and basement aquifers, allowing the estimation of groundwater recharge rates (Watson, Midgley, et al. 2022; Watson, Miller, et al. 2022).

The JAMS/J2000 considers the main bulk hydrological processes, components and storages within the hydrological cycle which include evapotranspiration, snow (not used for the Eerste) and groundwater, lateral routing between the HRUs as well as channel routing (Krause and Kralisch). In the model, modules are contained for climate input data temperature (T), windspeed (U), RH and RN (Figure 3) regionalization, estimation of potential and actual evapotranspiration, interception, soil water balance, groundwater balance as well as runoff routing in streams and channels (Base et al. 2001). Another aspect of the model is that it divides soil pore spaces into large pore storage (LPS) and middle pore storage (MPS) (Figure 3) based on soil profiles as well as the depth for effective rooting of the land use class of each Hydrological Response Unit (HRUs). The usable field capacity in the soil’s rooting corresponds to the MPS and the air capacity of the soil is denoted by the LPS (Machado et al. 2016). MPS represents pores that have a diameter of 0.2–50 μm with a volume equivalent to the usable field capacity water budget that only gets reduced by actual evapotranspiration. LPS, however, represents spaces that have a diameter of > 50 μm and a volume equivalent to the soil’s air capacity. The water that is in the LPS is not able to resist gravity and, as a result, LPS is filled through infiltration

and is emptied using lateral flow or interflow and vertical flow (percolation) process, which recharges groundwater and is thus considered the source of subsurface flow processes in the J2000 model (Penedo-Julien et al. 2018). Infiltration water gets distributed between the MPS and LPS, which is based on the distribution coefficient until these storages are filled or maximum infiltration is reached. Thereafter, infiltration excess water gets stored as depression storage (DPS) at the surface and when maximum DPS is reached, surface runoff gets generated, which is routed to the adjacent downslope spatial unit. The LPS outflow gets distributed as lateral runoff and percolation determined by the slope and calibration parameter (Meinhardt et al. 2018).

3.2.1 | Model Setup for the Eerste River Catchment

This study utilised an already existing base application of the JAMS/J2000 model of the Eerste River, which included one additional specific model adaptation considering reservoir release and operation (Watson, Midgley, et al. 2021; Watson, Birkel, et al. 2024). Previous applications of the JAMS/J2000 in the Western Cape do however show the reduced ability of the model to simulate baseflow during the wet season, as the model assumes continuous percolation causing overly linear groundwater recharge (Miller et al. 2018; Watson et al. 2018, 2019). The base model for JAMS/J2000 includes a standard: (1) HRU delineation of the modelling units, (2) sequence of model components and processes including input data regionalisation (Figure 3), (3) parameterization of soil, hydrogeology and land use, (4) evaluation of simulated versus observed streamflow and (5) calibration of model parameters within global

parameter ranges (i.e., using the historical weather data driving the model). The HRU delineation used the GRASS-HRU delineation procedure (Schwartz 2008) to generate HRUs, reach network with flow routing, sub-basins and watershed for the Eerste River. The input data for the HRU delineation included gauging station locations (four gauges: not all gauges used for calibration), a digital elevation model (DEM: Shuttle Radar Topography Mission: SRTM 90 m), map of land use (2013–2014 South African National Land-Cover dataset: GEOTERRAIMAGE), map of geology (1:250 000 geological map of the Western Cape, obtained from the Council of Geosciences) and global soil dataset (Harmonized World Soil Database Version 1.2: Nachtergaele et al. 2008). The HRU delineation procedures include the filling sinks within the DEM, calculation of DEM derivatives (slope, aspect, flow accumulation and flow direction), determining sub-basin extents and stream network using a threshold of minimum sub-basin area, overlay of DEM derivatives and map layer inputs and finally, minimum HRU size restrictions to remove sliver pixels (further detail of the HRU delineation is available in Watson et al. 2020; Watson, Kralisch, et al. 2021). Spatial interpolation of the input data was performed using inverse distance weighting for robust regionalization, even where weather station data gaps exist. The parameterization of land use required the use of literature values to estimate (1) albedo (%), (2) monthly surface resistances assuming sufficient water supply, (3) leaf area index (LAI) for vegetational growth periods, (4) effective vegetation heights for growth periods, (5) root depth

and (6) sealed grade value (impervious areas). The parameterization of hydrogeology for the model requires the estimation of (1) maximum storage capacity (RG1 and RG2max) and (2) storage coefficient (RG1 and RG2_k) for the upper (RG1) and lower aquifer (RG2), which are based on model expertise across the world of J2000 parameters. The climate station data used to drive the base model were taken from Watson, Midgley, et al. (2021) and Watson, Birkel, et al. (2024) but included weather records from 23 stations for precipitation, 13 stations for temperature (mean, min, max), 6 stations for RH, 8 stations for windspeed and 5 stations for RN for the periods 1980–1990. To allow for intercomparison with the historical projection, the station data were regionalized using the centroid of the projection. This projection regionalization was only done for the bias correction of the CORDEX-CORE models, to lump the station data into a ~25 km scale, analogous to a CORDEX grid cell and was not applied to the J2000-base simulation.

3.3 | Bias Correction of CORDEX Climate Projections

To determine the best method for bias correcting the projection data, both parametric and empirical quantile mapping methods were tested. Parametric methods include parametric transformation (PTF), while the empirical methods include empirical quantile (QUANT), robust empirical quantile

FIGURE 4 | Mean bias of climate models after bias correction, using the PTF (parametric transformation), SSPLIN (smoothing splines), QUANT (empirical quantile), RQUANT (robust empirical quantile) quantile mapping (QM) methods.

(RQUANT) and smoothing splines (SSPLIN) (Moradkhani and Sorooshian 2009). The historical data of the climate models were quantile-mapped with the corresponding observed historical data during the same period (1980–2005), with the bias then calculated against the same observed historical data (Figure 4). The bias of the historical runs for the quantile-mapped historical climate model data was then visualised using heatmaps. The JAMS/J2000 model was then run using the four QM methods for the period with projection data (2006–2016) being statistically downscaled by observed reference

data (1980–1990). The outcome of these results determined the quantile mapping method with the best performance, which was used for analysis of the near future (2024–2053). The selected QM method with the best overall performance (based on (a) how well it reduced climate model bias and (b) the J2000 efficiencies) was the PTF method. This method exhibited moderate bias throughout all climate variables and models and had the best KGE values in the simulation run, as well as the second lowest positive bias (Figure 4). Therefore, the PTF method has been selected as the best QM method for future climate

FIGURE 5 | (a) Average yearly and (b) monthly precipitation for J2000_base and bias corrected HadCCLM5, HadREGCM4, HadREMO, MpiESMCCLM5, MpiESMREGCM4, MpiESMREMO, NorESMCCLM5, NorESMREGCM4, NorESMREMO projections from 2006 to 2016.

TABLE 2 | Summary of the model parameters used for J2000_base with sensitivities of model parameters during the Monte Carlo runs for J2000_base and projections HadCCLM5, HadREGCM4, HadREM0, MpiESMCCLM5, MpiESMREGCM4, NorESMREGCM4, NorESMCCLM5, NorESMREM0 using the Nash–Sutcliffe Efficiency in standard form: NSE; Nash and Sutcliffe 1970 and downstream gauging station.

Name of parameter	Type	Description of parameter	J2000		Cal		MCA parameter sets		J2000-base		J2000-HadCCLM5		J2000-MpiCCLM5		J2000-NorCCLM5		J2000-MpiREGCM4		J2000-MpiREM0	
			Calibration range	Optimal value	MCA lower bounds	MCA upper bounds	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	
AC_Adaptation	Soil-water	Multiplies the volume of the large pore storage of soil	0.7–1.5	1.50	1.35	1.65	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.05	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.21	0.21	0.19	0.19
FC_Adaptation	Soil-water	Multiplies the volume of the middle pore storage of soil	0.7–1.5	0.82	0.74	0.90	0.14	0.12	0.14	0.12	0.05	0.05	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.07	0.07	0.10	0.10	0.10
soilLinRed	ET	Actual ET parameter, governing the reduction of potential ET according to the soil moisture	0–1	0.99	0.89	1.09	0.22	0.23	0.22	0.23	0.17	0.17	0.18	0.18	0.19	0.19	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17
soilDiffMPSLPS	Soil-water	MPS/LPS diffusion coefficient	0–10	2.50	2.25	2.75														
soilDistMPSLPS	Soil-water	MPS/LPS distribution coefficient for inflow	0–10	6.13	5.51	6.74														
soilMaxInfSummer	Soil-water	The maximum infiltration capacity of soil in the summer period (northern hemisphere)	0–200	160.81	144.73	176.89														
soilMaxInfWinter	Soil-water	The maximum infiltration capacity of soil in the winter period (northern hemisphere)	0–200	180.85	162.76	198.93														

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

Name of parameter	Type	Description of parameter	J2000 Calibration range	Cal	MCA parameter sets		J2000-base Sensitivity (%)	J2000-HadCCLM5 Sensitivity (%)	J2000-MpiCCLM5 Sensitivity (%)	J2000-NorCCLM5 Sensitivity (%)	J2000-MpiREGCM4 Sensitivity (%)	J2000-MpiREMO Sensitivity (%)
					MCA lower bounds	MCA upper bounds						
soilConcRD1	Soil-water	Surface runoff delay parameter	0.5–2	2.00	1.80	2.20	0.20	0.21	0.14	0.13	0.18	0.15
soilConcRD2	Soil-water	Interflow delay parameter	0.5–5	4.42	3.98	4.87	0.08	0.13	0.17	0.14	0.12	0.16
soilOutLPS	Soil-water	Outflow parameter of the large pore storage	0–10	2.05	1.84	2.25	0.13	0.12	0.03	0.03	0.05	0.04
soilMaxPerc	Soil-water	Conductivity adaption parameter for leaching water to the groundwater storage	0–20	12.89	11.60	14.18	0.14	0.10	0.13	0.14	0.12	0.12
soilLatVert	Soil-water	Distribution coefficient for LPS outflow to lateral and vertical flow path	0.1–10	0.10	0.09	0.11	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02
gwRG1RG2dist	Groundwater	distribution parameter for the slow and fast groundwater runoff	0–1	0.80	0.72	0.88						
gwRG1Fact	Groundwater	fast groundwater (slow interflow) delay	0–10	8.71	7.84	9.58						
gwRG2Fact	Groundwater	Base flow delay	0–10	9.90	8.91	10.89						
flowrouteTA	Flow routing	Stream routing parameter (overall dampening of the hydrograph)	0–20	10.41	9.37	11.45	0.04	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.04

projections under the future forcing scenarios in this study. The selected QM method overestimated the precipitation for the catchment on average between 9% and 16% across all the projections (Figure 5).

3.4 | Model Performance Evaluation and Uncertainty

To evaluate the model performance of the historical projections compared to the base model, the Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE; Nash and Sutcliffe 1970), NSE in logarithmic form (logNSE), Kling–Gupta Efficiency (KGE; Gupta et al. 2009) and bias were used. The calibrated parameter set obtained with local station data was applied unchanged to all simulations with climate model inputs; no recalibration was done for each projection, to directly evaluate projection-induced differences in simulated flows. While the evaluation of the base model involved a calibration procedure for the periods 1999–2006, the historical projections formed part of the validation of the model. Additionally, the base model validation was performed from 2006 to 2021 using the observed climate data as the J2000 input. J2000 for this study ran at a daily timestep, but due to the coarse resolution of the projection and the intended use as a monthly aggregation, the model evaluation criteria for the projections were converted to monthly efficiencies. To understand the parameter uncertainty difference between the base model and the historical projections, a Monte Carlo Analysis (MCA) was performed (Table 2). The uncertainty analysis included the evaluation of the difference in uncertainty between the ESMs over the RSMs by doing two separate comparisons. An evaluation was performed by comparing parameter uncertainty of (1) CCLM5 (RSM) within the HadGCM, MpiESM and NorESM, as well as (2) MpiESM (ESM) using CCLM5, REGCM4 and REMO. The

MCA utilised the base model parameters as a midpoint and scaled parameters according to $\pm 10\%$ (Table 2). Final analysis included using an artificial neural network to calculate the relative sensitivity of the most influential J2000 parameters, namely: factors used to scale soil-water air and field capacity (AC and FC adaptation), surface runoff and interflow delay parameters (SoilConcRD1, SoilConcRD2), outflow parameter for LPS (SoilOutLPS), maximum percolation rate of the soil (SoilMaxPerc), diffusion coefficient from LPS between lateral and vertical flow paths (SoilLatVertDist) and streamflow routing/dampening parameter of the hydrograph (flowrouteTA).

4 | Results

4.1 | Simulated Streamflow Using Historical Projection Versus Measured Data

The base J2000 model had an overall good simulation for high (NSE) and low flows (LogNSE) for the downstream gauge, while the monthly performance using station-driven JAMS/J2000 was consistently better (Figure 6 and Table 3). Upstream daily performance was satisfactory for both high and low flows, while KGE was also satisfactory (Moriyas et al. 2007). In contrast, the CORDEX-CORE driven simulations exhibited generally poorer performance, particularly for high flows, which is attributed to the coarse spatial resolution of the climate projections (Table 3).

The historical HadGEM projections showed considerable bias in the simulated streamflow seasonality, where more streamflow was generated after August–September compared to the usual streamflow high of June/July in the observed data (Figure 6). MpiESM and NorESM show better seasonality in the simulated streamflow, aligning with the observed streamflow seasonality but had a lower overall efficiency than HadGCM (Figure 6).

FIGURE 6 | Average monthly observed and simulated streamflow using the JAMS/J2000 model showing the simulated streamflow using J2000_base and J2000 driven by bias corrected projections from HadCCLM5, HadREGCM4, HadREMO, MpiESMCCCLM5, MpiESMREGCM4, MpiESMREMO, NorESMCCCLM5, NorESMREGCM4, NorESMREMO for the upstream (Jonkershoek) and downstream (Kleinwelmoed) streamflow gauges from 2006 to 2016.

While there is deviation in the simulated streamflow even using the local weather station data, the calibration balanced the performance between the upstream and downstream efficiency. The MpiESM showed the most similarity in terms of the simulated streamflow seasonality, but NorESM showed similar good monthly hydrographs across both the downstream and upstream gauges. In general, J2000, driven by the CORDEX-CORE models, overestimated streamflow compared to the observations.

4.2 | Simulated Hydrological Processes

The simulated flow components of the J2000 model, driven by local climate station data, predict a high proportion of baseflow contribution to streamflow (56%), followed by interflow (34%) and surface runoff (10%) (Figures 7–9, transparent lines). Most of the overall baseflow was simulated in the wet period, but the main proportion was simulated for the dry season across the base model (January–March, August–December). The HadGCM had a large difference in the simulated flow components compared to the base model, due to the overall late rainfall seasonality in the historical projection (Figure 7). RCP 2.6 and 8.5 of HadGCM showed better agreement with the base J2000 model than the historical project. HadCCLM5 suggests a more equal contribution from interflow, baseflow under RCP 2.6, but enhanced surface runoff under RCP 8.5. HadREGCM4 and HadREMO for both RCPs showed more similarities to the J2000 base with streamflow and flow component peaks in July.

For MpiESM, CCLM5 RSM showed the most similarity to the J2000 base model but exhibited a split in streamflow peak for June and August (Figure 8). REGCM4 and REMO also displayed high hydrological process similarity to the J2000 base model, but with earlier onset of the seasonal rising hydrograph limb and more simulated interflow. RCP 2.6 for MpiESM suggested a later onset of flows and a minor reduction of all the flow components. RCP 8.5 showed further reductions in simulated flow components and further onsets in the rising and falling limbs for the wet period (May–July). For most of the models, surface runoff showed minor future changes compared to baseflow. MpiESMCCLM5, NorESMCCLM5, NorESMREGCM4 and NorESMREMO showed a similar peak split in streamflow peak (observed in interflow) in June and August (Figure 9). MpiESMREGCM4 had the highest similarity to the J2000 base model in terms of the simulated hydrological flow components. The future RCP 2.6 and 8.5 suggested the largest reduction in simulated baseflow, with reductions in baseflow during the dry period (January–April) compared to the J2000 base. NorESMCCLM5 RCP 2.6 and 8.5 suggested the largest reduction in simulated baseflow compared to NorESMREGCM4 and NorESMREMO.

4.3 | Projected Future Simulated Streamflow and Water Balance (2024–2053)

The RCP 2.6 and 8.5 for HadGEM all show extreme drought risk for the dry period (January–April) of the year, with large

FIGURE 7 | Simulated flow components (surface runoff, interflow and baseflow proportions) for HadGCMCCLM5, HadGCMRegCM4 and HadGCMREMO under historical, RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 scenarios. Results are compared with the J2000 base model calibrated using local climate station data. Transparent panels represent the historical simulations used for comparison with future projections.

FIGURE 8 | Simulated flow components (surface runoff, interflow and baseflow proportions) for MPI-ESMCCLM5, MPIESMRegCM4 and MPIESMREMO under historical, RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 conditions, compared with the J2000 base model calibrated using local climate station data. Transparent panels represent the corresponding historical simulations used for reference in the future projections.

deviations from the historical conditions (Figure 10). Likewise, MpiESMCCLM5 and NorESMREMO project an increase in extreme drought risk under different RCP conditions. An extension of the dry season was simulated using all the RSMs for MpiESM, with a loss of high flows using CCLM5 and REGCM4. Similar loss of high flows was simulated for NorESMCCLM5 and NorESMREMO, with an increase in flood risk being simulated using NorESM REGCM4. Across all the ESMs and RSMs, the future 2.6 and 8.5 RCP streamflow projections suggest lower yearly precipitation (Figure 11). Likewise, RCP 8.5 suggests an overall reduction in streamflow except using HadREGCM4. RCP 2.6 had higher simulated streamflow using MpiESMCCLM5 than historical, but on average was also lower than the historical projection. Simulated actual ET is variable across the models and with most models was lower under the future scenario due to the availability of less precipitation, impacting the availability of soil moisture for transpiration.

4.4 | Model Parameter Uncertainty

The analysis of the impact of the most important parameters for J2000 suggested that HADCCLM5 was the most similar to J2000 base, with linear reduction of soil moisture (SoilLinRed) being the most sensitive parameter across all the model parameters (Figure 12). NorCCLM5, MPICCLM5 and MpiREMO had similar sensitivity, being most impacted by the scaling of air capacity AC_adaptation. The variability of the model

parameter sensitivities was higher for ESMs compared to the RSMs, suggesting that the different ESMs have more impact than the RSMs.

5 | Discussion

5.1 | Simulating Hydrological Processes With Climate Projections

The calibration procedure in rainfall-runoff modelling is commonly used to adjust model parameters to improve process simulation, often dependent on the match between simulated and observed streamflow (Moradkhani and Sorooshian 2009), but where isotope or tracer data can also be used to improve overall robustness (Dehaspe et al. 2018; Watson, Birkel, et al. 2024). The calibration of models is more related to utilising a single set of model parameters or various parameter values based on whether they are Pareto-optimal. When running a set of different projections with a different spatial resolution and historical data bias, there is often a large mismatch in the simulated streamflow. In this study, instead of recalibrating the J2000 for each different projection (ESM and RCM combination), we analyse the differences in the simulated streamflow and flow components compared to a base model calibrated with local weather station data. Thereafter, we compared which projection best resembles the observed streamflow and flow components estimated by the base model.

Earth System Model (ESM) NorESM (Norwegian Earth System Model)

FIGURE 9 | Simulated flow components (surface runoff, interflow and baseflow proportions) for NorESMCClM5, NorESMRegCM4 and NorESMREMO under historical, RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 conditions, compared with the J2000 base model calibrated using local climate station data. Transparent panels represent the corresponding historical simulations used for reference in the future projections.

The bias in precipitation seasonality had the largest impact on the simulated flow components, in particular, surface runoff and interflow. Interestingly, the climate projections with the most evident seasonal differences to the local weather data had a lower total bias compared to projections that captured the seasonality in the historical data well (Table 3). The models exhibiting reduced streamflow bias do not, however, have a consistently lower precipitation amount than the other models across the ESMs and RCMs (Figure 5) but have more simulated evapotranspiration, resulting in less simulated streamflow (Figure 12). The seasonal bias, therefore, increased simulated evapotranspiration during the dry season, where there was a higher demand for water with more water available due to the offset in precipitation seasonality. But these impacts are less compared to the ‘unrealistically’ high simulation of baseflow in the base model and the projection models. Such high total baseflow simulations are common in hydrological models for the Western Cape region (Watson et al. 2018, 2020; Watson, Miller et al. 2021) and the use of isotope tracers has had success in providing more ‘realistic’ baseflow simulations (Watson et al. 2023; Watson, Birkel, et al. 2024) for the region. There is, however, still an inherent issue in that the groundwater recharge simulation follows a constant linear or exponential outflow of percolation from the unsaturated zone into the saturated zone, but in reality, recharge in the Western Cape is episodic or threshold-driven (Watson, Birkel, et al. 2024). While the standard daily J2000

has been widely applied in the region, the more complex layered soil module version of J2000-s (Fink et al. 2007) could offer a solution to better constrain recharge simulations and could form a more standard recommendation in many semi-arid environments, as smaller events (<20 mm/day) could be excluded from contributing to simulated percolation and only cycle within the soil zone. Because the calibrated model likely overestimates absolute baseflow contributions (Watson et al. 2023), the projected reductions in baseflow (though directionally robust) should be interpreted as relative changes rather than precise volumetric predictions. Incorporating process enhancements (e.g., a threshold-based recharge model such as J2000-s) in future studies could improve the realism of baseflow projections.

The universal availability of statistically downscaled climate change projections is limited to globally available projections such as CORDEX-CORE, as well as specific products developed by different research groups. For the Eerste River, a 25 km projection was the highest spatial resolution available at the time of the study (2022). However, due to the elevation difference between the mountainous and valley regions exceeding ~1500 m, a high-resolution downscaled product (5–10 km resolution) is required for more nuanced analysis. The dominance of ESM uncertainty from this study and the need for considerable bias correction are likely applicable to other basins in the Western Cape, similar Mediterranean-climate

Earth System Model (ESM)

FIGURE 10 | Yearly average simulated streamflow for HadCCLM5, HadREGCM4, HadREMO, MpiESMCCLM5, MpiESMREGCM4, MpiESMREMO, NorESMCCLM5, NorESMREGCM4, NorESMREMO projections under historical (2006–2016), RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 (2024–2053).

regions or small mountainous catchments. CMIP6 (Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6), with a target for improved resolution, will hopefully fill this void, but might still require bias correction for areas with high altitudinal variability.

5.2 | Projected Hydrological Changes in the Eerste River and Neighbouring Catchments

The Western Cape of South Africa has a history of intense droughts (2015–2018, 2010–2012, 2003–2004 and 1998–2000), which typically range between one and three years in length (Watson, Midgley, et al. 2022). Most of these droughts were characterised by shortfalls in precipitation during March, April and May. In some years, however, droughts influenced the wet season by reducing rainfall in June, July and August (e.g., 2000–2003 and 2017) (Watson, Miller, et al. 2022). Precipitation in winter during drought years was associated with large-scale atmospheric circulation patterns dominated by high-pressure weather regimes, indicative of dry conditions (Mandavya et al. 2025). Likewise, the analysis of weather regimes for the Western Cape suggested an increase in the frequency of dry weather regimes in contrast to wet weather regimes post 2010. Previous research has also suggested that an alteration in storm track and local changes in uplift are expected to influence the precipitation from autumn to winter in the future (Jack et al. 2022). These projected changes aligned

with the CORDEX-CORE models run through J2000 in this study, particularly MpiESMCCLM5 and NorESMREMO.

Previous studies (Du Plessis and Kalima 2021; Kibii and Du Plessis 2024) suggested that streamflow is projected to decrease by 8%–18%, which aligns well with 10%–22% (Q1–Q3) predicted under RCP 2.6 for the near future from J2000. RCP 8.5 in comparison simulated an 8%–26% (Q1–Q3) decrease for the near future from J2000 (2024–2053). Country-wide projections suggest that the Western Cape could be subject to as much as a 25% reduction in future Mean Annual Runoff by 2070 (using ACRU-4 driven by C-CAM) (Schulze et al. 2005). The 2023 national assessment suggests relative changes in mean annual streamflow for Quaternary Catchment G22H under RCP8.5 of 25% in the near future (2015–2044) and 51% in the distant future (2070–2099), relative to the historical period (1961–1990) (Schütte et al. 2023). A consensus from the literature and this study is that the Eerste River is likely to become a more drought-prone area under changing precipitation patterns and this is expected to decrease streamflow in the near future. A reduction in streamflow means that future water management will become more difficult, as the region has an over-reliance on surface water supply from reservoirs. Improving the mix of different water sources (groundwater, surface water, desalination) remains the most viable solution for reducing drought risk in the region, but this requires more active monitoring (such as groundwater level measurements, water quality analysis).

Earth System Model (ESM)

FIGURE 11 | Overall water balance of future projections for HadCCLM5, HadREGCM4, HadREMO, MpiESMCCLM5, MpiESMREGCM4, MpiESMREMO, NorESMCCLM5, NorESMREGCM4, NorESMREMO under historical (2006–2016), RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 (2024–2053) where dS = change in storage, ET = evapotranspiration, P = precipitation, Q = streamflow.

FIGURE 12 | Results of the Monte Carlo analysis (MCA) used to understand the relative sensitivity of the different model parameters using the Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency NSE (Nash and Sutcliffe 1970), the downstream gauging station Klein Welmoed for J2000_base, HadCCLM5, HadREGCM4, HadREMO, MpiESMCCLM5, MpiESMREGCM4, MpiESMREMO, NorESMCCLM5, NorESMREGCM4, NorESMREMO projections under historical conditions (2006–2016). (a) Earth System Model and (b) RSM parameter uncertainty evaluation.

5.3 | Implications of Near-Future Projections for Water Management in the Eerste River

Climate change attribution studies, which separate the impacts of climate change from other anthropogenic activities

such as land use management and reservoir releases, are required to determine future risks (Zhai et al. 2018). Often, attributing hydrometeorological disasters to climate change can be difficult due to natural variability and other human impacts affecting water management. Flood risk in South Africa, for

example, is often impacted by reservoir releases and whether the flood wave is met and/or contributed to by reservoir operations. Usually, to ensure that there is enough water supply in reservoirs to last throughout the dry season, especially in Mediterranean regions such as the Western Cape of South Africa, there is a hesitancy to release and rather store as much water as possible during the wet season, a decision also facing drought-prone regions like those in Australia. However, flood control measures have recently been problematic in 2023 for catchments in the Western Cape, such as the Eerste and neighbouring Berg River, where, at the height of the high flows, reservoir releases could further compound the flood peak (Heleen 2023). Likewise, reductions in reservoir releases during extensive dry conditions can have negative impacts on water quality, riparian ecosystems and ensure the river ecological reserve is being met.

These projections from this study suggest a need to improve seasonal or sub-seasonal forecasting and nowcasting to better manage floods and extended dry periods. Such systems need to anticipate early dam/reservoir releases before extremes such as cut-off lows occur. Methods of adaptation, such as managed aquifer recharge, are currently being explored in the neighbouring catchment (Cape Flats) and are something that the Eerste catchment could use for adaptation. Further research into mountain headwater hydrological processes and variability is important, given the future projections and the results from this study. However, high-resolution km-scale climate change projections are needed in these catchments to attribute extreme events to an increase in intensity of precipitation, such as recent studies done on the 2022 Durban floods (Engelbrecht et al. 2025). While km-scale climate change projections are required for hydrological attribution, such computationally intensive products are less necessary for drought simulation, as shown by this study.

6 | Conclusion

Climate change is impacting water availability across the globe and many regions have experienced an increase in extreme events such as droughts and floods. The availability of different projections of the future climate includes results from coarse resolution ESMs (100–300 km) with nested RSMs, which aim to provide refined boundaries and more local factors to produce higher resolution projections (< 25 km). However, the variability of different RCPs, different ESMs and RSMs means there is often a range in the variability of future projections. Evaluating globally available ESMs between extreme (RCP 8.5) and conservative (RCP 2.6) scenarios for the near future is important for regions experiencing an increase in drought occurrences. In this study, we were able to understand near-future potential impacts on water availability for the Eerste River in South Africa, a catchment of high-water importance and which has experienced both drought and intense floods from 2015 to 2025. While the coarse resolution of CMIP-5 impacts the rainfall–runoff model's ability to replicate streamflow using the projections, a consensus between simulations using the projections and the prevailing literature is that near-future reductions in streamflow and extension of the dry season are expected. The resolution of CMIP-5 was, however, too coarse to provide good intercomparison with

the benchmark model and the simulation of future and present. Likewise, hydrological flow components (baseflow, interflow and surface runoff) could be improved using tracer or isotope-enabled models, which provide more relevant data for hydrological processes. More extreme precipitation patterns and shifts in rainy season timing are likely scenarios for the catchment, consistent with our ensemble projections. As Mediterranean climates around the world begin to experience more frequent droughts, higher-resolution projections are recommended to improve simulated model results, as shown by this study. The availability of isotope-enabled climate projections can likewise improve process simulation of models and reduce near-future model uncertainty.

Acknowledgements

The views and opinions expressed here are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union nor the granting authority, which cannot be held responsible for them. The authors would like to thank two anonymous reviewers for the comments and suggestions which improved the quality of this article.

Funding

This article was funded by the European Union under the grant agreement No GA 101082048 (MAR2PROTECT project) and the Water Research Commission (C2024/205-01587). AW also acknowledge support from the Bundesministerium für Bildung, Technik und Raumfahrt (BMFTR) Grant 02WAS1713A “Co-design of a hydrometeorological information system for sustainable water resources management in southern Africa (CO-Hydim-SA)”.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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